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Final Dissertation

How Regulatory Failures Led to the 2007- 2008 Financial Crisis
- Assessing Post- Crisis reforms and the Lessons Learned on Systemic Risk Management.

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the systemic causes of the 2007–2008 financial crisis, with a central focus on regulatory failures in the oversight of subprime mortgage lending and the securitization of high-risk assets. Using a pragmatist mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative financial analysis with qualitative case studies, the research examines the interconnected roles of banking system fragility, flawed financial innovation, and delayed regulatory responses. Quantitative findings based on time-series modeling and regression analysis reveal strong correlations between asset quality deterioration, rising unemployment, and increasing bankruptcy rates during the crisis. Complementary case analyses of institutions such as Lehman Brothers, AIG, and Citigroup illustrate institutional mismanagement, leverage excesses, and inadequate regulatory interventions. The study further evaluates the effectiveness of post-crisis reforms, particularly the Dodd-Frank Act and Basel III, in mitigating systemic risks and enhancing financial stability. While notable progress has been made, the persistence of shadow banking and emerging deregulation pressures highlight the need for continued regulatory vigilance. The findings offer insights into strengthening early warning systems and shaping forward-looking, adaptive financial governance.

Acknowledgement

This bachelor's thesis concludes my undergraduate studies and serves as a reflection of the knowledge and insights I gained throughout my academic career. I'd like to express my heartfelt appreciation to my supervisor, whose guidance, encouragement, and constructive feedback were invaluable in shaping this work. I am especially grateful to Niels Brock Copenhagen Business College for providing a supportive academic environment that has supported me grow as a student and researcher. The program's accreditation by De Montfort University added significant value to the course design, that combined strong academics with practical relevance. Beyond academics, this work has a deep personal significance. Coming from a business-oriented family, I witnessed the impact of the 2007-2008 financial crisis firsthand. These experiences inspired my commitment to this research and continue to fuel my interest in finance and economics. I am determined to contribute meaningfully to the field in my future career, motivated by both personal connection and professional ambition. Finance and the economic industry are more than just areas of study for me; they are deeply integrated in who I am and who I want to become.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Financial crises, as explained in various theories, involve disruptions in financial markets characterized by a sudden and widespread drop in asset prices, such as stocks, bonds, or real estate. These crises are often accompanied by a sharp rise in interest rates, driven by actual or projected declines in asset returns. Such declines may result from negative real shocks, including rising input costs, unfavorable terms of trade, or financial shocks, such as fluctuating interest rates, currency devaluations, or the withdrawal of government guarantees. (Radke, 2005)

Furthermore, Banking crisis, it has been discussed by (Allen, Babus and Carletti, 2009a), banking crisis is rooted in the fundamental role of banks as financial intermediaries channeling funds from depositors and short-term capital markets to those seeking investments, moreover Banks benefit from diversified portfolios, offer risk-sharing and engage in maturity transformation, on the other hand, financial distress in the banking system significantly has impacts economic activity, contributing to credit contractions and low GDP growth. (Allen, Babus and Carletti, 2009a)

To elaborate more, one of the two theories of banking crises sees them as random, self-fulfilling panics, unrelated to economic fundamentals, where depositor beliefs trigger runs, on the other hand, second theory links crises to the business cycle, there, economic downturns and poor asset performance prompt withdrawals, moreover, model integrating banks in economic frameworks highlight how financial shocks disrupt liquidity and asset pricing, in addition, regulatory frameworks such as Basel II, usually contributes to fluctuation, failing to prevent credit contraction during recessions. (Allen, Babus and Carletti, 2009b)

The **2008** global financial crisis, that is marked one of the most severe economic collapses in recent history, was rooted in the systemic failure of financial markets and banking systems, both of which is deeply interconnected, nonetheless, the crisis highlighted financial and banking crises going hand in and amplifying economic disruptions through liquidity shortages, asset prices collapses and widespread institutional failures.

“The 2007-09 economic crisis was deep and protracted enough to become known as "the Great Recession" and was followed by what was, by some measures, a long but unusually slow recovery.”

(Anon, 2013c)

Following that, the crisis ultimately led to the **Great Recession**, as home prices fell over 20% between 2007 and 2011, triggering uncertainty in mortgage-related assets, resulting widespread market disruptions. Although the Federal Reserve, in collaboration with other agencies, worked to stabilize financial systems and limit economic damage, the recovery was slow and marked by severe economic contraction. However, without the Federal Reserve’s intervention, the consequences could have been far worse. (Anon, 2013c)

The research aims to analyze the systemic causes of 2008 global financial crisis, focusing on the interconnectedness of financial and banking crises, by examining the role of banking systems as intermediaries, the failure to monitor market imbalances, and the broader global impacts, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms that contributed to the crisis.

Moreover, the primary focus of this research is to analyze **regulatory failures** in the oversight of **subprime loans and mortgage-backed securities** and their contribution to the 2007-2008 financial crisis in the United States. The study will also assess the effectiveness of **post-crisis regulatory reforms** in addressing these failures. In this context, the research will examine:

To achieve this, the study will explore the following key areas:

- **Regulatory Gaps and Risk Exposure:** Examining how **inadequate oversight** enabled the unchecked growth of **subprime loan securitization and mortgage-backed securities**, amplifying financial instability.
- **Systemic Vulnerabilities:** Investigating how these gaps **exacerbated systemic risks** within the **U.S. financial system**, contributing to market imbalances.
- **Institutional Failures:** Assessing the **collapse of major financial institutions**, particularly **Lehman Brothers**, and its implications for the fragility of the regulatory framework at the time.
- **Post-Crisis Reforms:** Analyzing the **key provisions of the Dodd-Frank Act (2009-2010)** and evaluating their effectiveness in **reducing financial vulnerabilities and preventing similar crises**.
- **Lessons for Future Regulation:** Identifying insights from the crisis that can inform **future regulatory policies** to enhance financial stability and prevent systemic failures.

The key provision of the Dodd-Frank Act introduced in 2009-2010, and how effectively have they mitigated similar risks in the post-crisis era.

- “The Dodd- Frank Wall Street Reform and Consumer Protection Act of 2010 was designed to increase financial stability and prevent future devastation from financial crises.” (Baily, Klein and Schardin, 2017)

Lessons that can be drawn from the crisis to guide future regulatory policies and prevent similar financial disruption.

As highlighted by the Financial Crisis Inquiry Commission (FCIC), the crisis caused significant economic and social upheaval, with millions losing their jobs and homes while the economy struggled to recover, making the topic crucial to understand. (United States, 2010)

Chapter 2: Literature Review

“Year-end data suggest that 2001 was a strong year for housing despite a 9-month-long recession. New records were set and old records challenged for many housing market indicators.”(Anon, 2001)

The **seeds of the 2008 financial crisis** were planted in the **late 1990s**, particularly with the **repeal of the Glass-Steagall Act in 1999** under the **Gramm-Leach-Bliley Act**, which allowed commercial banks to merge with investment banks, **increasing exposure to risky financial products** (Crawford, 2011). Following the **dot-com bubble burst in 2001**, the **Federal Reserve slashed interest rates**, creating an era of **easy credit and excessive risk-taking** (Johnson and Kwak, 2010).

Financial institutions **exploited regulatory loopholes**, loading **risky loans** onto their balance sheets through **Structured Investment Vehicles (SIVs)** (Acharya & Richardson, 2009). (Acharya and Richardson, 2009)The removal of Glass-Steagall’s restrictions **enabled banks to engage in high-risk trading** while handling consumer deposits, **fueling the housing bubble**. When the **bubble burst**, these practices led to widespread insolvencies and the freezing of global credit markets (Johnson & Kwak, 2010).

Simultaneously, according to the FEDs, from the starting in **2001 to 2003**, the extension of mortgage credit to high-risk borrowers fueled the housing boom. Financial innovations, such as private-label mortgage-backed securities, facilitated subprime lending and pushed up the rate of homeownership. However, flawed risk models underestimated the vulnerabilities of these new products. Inflated house prices, particularly in supply-constrained markets, spawned an unsustainable self-reinforcing cycle of speculation. These dynamics masked the growing fragility of the financial system and ultimately set the stage for the crisis.

The period from **2004 to 2006**, The New Financial Architecture considerably facilitated excessive securitization of subprime mortgages and other problematic, complex financial instruments like collateralized debt obligations, or CDOs. Most of the obscure products camouflaged risks, fostered by wrong incentives and irresponsible leveraging when institutions opted for short-run profits at the expense of long-run stability. According to(Crotty, 2009a),the "originate and distribute" model was the hallmark of such an approach, which implanted the frailties into the very guts of the system. This model allowed financial institutions to distribute their risky loans to investors of all kinds around the world, yet still retain pieces of the riskiest assets for their books to keep the profit cycle going. Crotty further adds that without any regulatory controls during those times, such vulnerabilities were able to reach a full bloom, and the system turned out to be so fragile that even a minor disturbance in it shook the foundations of global stability.

One report, *U.S. Housing Market Conditions, Fourth Quarter 2001 Summary* (2001), highlights those regulatory authorities made **little effort to address growing financial risks**, allowing institutions to **exploit loopholes and rely on faulty risk assessment models**. This **lack of oversight** was particularly evident in the widespread issuance of **adjustable-rate subprime loans** without adequate testing of **borrower creditworthiness**. By **2006**, when interest rates **reset to higher levels**, many borrowers **struggled to make payments**, leading to a **sharp rise in defaults**. Combined with

the **halt in rising home prices**, these defaults **exposed systemic risks** embedded in the **housing and financial markets**. This marked the **beginning of a broader breakdown**, where **regulatory complacency and speculative behavior** converged, **amplifying the crisis**. (Anon, 2001)

The financial crisis began in **2007** as the housing market, after decades of expansion, started to contract. Residential construction declined, and home prices began a sharp fall from their 2006 peak. Subprime mortgage defaults surged, sparking global concerns over the value of mortgage-backed securities (MBS) and collateralized debt obligations (CDOs). This uncertainty eroded confidence and liquidity in financial markets. By **August 2007**, pressures emerged in the asset-backed commercial paper market as investors grew wary of subprime-related assets. Losses mounted for major financial institutions, and interbank lending tightened, highlighting the systemic risks embedded in the financial system. While the Federal Reserve intervened with liquidity measures and rate cuts, these efforts only mitigated short-term liquidity problems without addressing deeper structural flaws. (Anon, 2013b)

As, (Mishkin, 2010) argues that the financial system's over-reliance on poorly understood innovations like securitization amplified systemic risks. Limited oversight allowed subprime lending to flourish, creating vulnerabilities that were underestimated by financial institutions. Although the Federal Reserve's interventions in **2007** were crucial, they failed to prevent the full-scale collapse of 2008, revealing the fragility of the financial system.

By 2008, the crisis reached its peak. The collapse of Bear Stearns and Lehman Brothers led to widespread panic and a freezing of credit markets. The government bailed out AIG to avoid further systemic failures, while the Troubled Asset Relief Program (TARP) injected capital into banks. Despite these efforts, the crisis plunged the economy into a severe recession marked by sharp GDP declines and soaring unemployment. (Arner, 2009) highlights that the events of 2008 exposed deep flaws in financial practices and regulatory frameworks.

As the crisis led to a **freeze in interbank lending and massive liquidity shortages**, the **U.S. government was forced to bail out AIG** to prevent a total financial meltdown (Khademian, 2011). In response, the government enacted the **Troubled Asset Relief Program (TARP)**, injecting **\$700 billion** into the financial system to **recapitalize banks, stabilize financial institutions, and restore credit flow**.

Simultaneously, the **Federal Reserve** introduced several **emergency measures**, including:

- **Lowering interest rates to near-zero levels** to encourage borrowing and liquidity.
- **Launching quantitative easing (QE)** to purchase **mortgage-backed securities (MBS) and government bonds**, injecting liquidity into financial markets.
- **Establishing emergency lending programs**, such as the **Term Auction Facility (TAF)** and the **Commercial Paper Funding Facility (CPFF)**, to provide liquidity to struggling banks and corporations.
- **Guaranteeing money market mutual funds** to prevent panic withdrawals.

Despite these interventions, the **U.S. economy still plunged into a deep recession**, with **GDP contracting by 4.3%** and **unemployment doubling to 10%**. These structural failures in **financial**

systems and regulatory oversight ultimately prompted the introduction of **major reforms, such as the Dodd-Frank Act**, to address **systemic risks** and enhance **market stability**.

In **2009**, governments and regulatory institutions globally confronted the fallout of the financial crisis and began addressing its systemic causes. The U.S. government continued implementing unprecedented interventions quantitative easing by the Federal Reserve, to stabilize financial markets and support economic recovery, (Crotty, 2009b), legislative discussions for the Dodd-Frank Act began, focusing on higher capital requirements, improved transparency in derivatives markets, and mechanisms to resolve failing institutions without taxpayer-funded bailouts, economic contraction and high unemployment of **2009** amplified political pressure for reform, culminating in the drafting of Dodd-Frank to enhance financial stability and restore public trust in the financial system.

Accordingly, it was a comprehensive legislative response to the 2008 financial crisis. Its purpose was to address systemic risks in the financial system, prevent future crises, and protect consumers from abusive financial practices. Key measures included the creation of the **Financial Stability Oversight Council (FSOC)** to monitor systemic risks, the **Orderly Liquidation Authority** to resolve failing financial firms without taxpayer bailouts, and the **Consumer Financial Protection Bureau (CFPB)** to safeguard consumer interests. The Act imposed stricter regulations on derivatives trading, required banks to retain credit risk in securitized assets, and prohibited proprietary trading through the **Volcker Rule**. By targeting regulatory gaps and reducing reliance on taxpayer-funded bailouts, Dodd-Frank aimed to enhance financial stability and restore confidence in the U.S. financial system. (Anon, 2013a)

Post-crisis, financial regulations significantly strengthened market stability, though challenges remain. Key advancements included tiered regulations based on the size and systemic importance of financial institutions, stricter capital and liquidity requirements to improve financial resilience, and the implementation of stress testing to assess banks' ability to withstand economic shocks. These measures have enhanced the resilience of systemically important institutions, reducing their dependence on short-term funding and mitigating financial instability risks. Furthermore, (Tarullo, 2019) highlights unresolved issues, particularly the under-regulation of shadow banking, where risks continue to grow outside the regulatory perimeter, the framework for macroprudential regulation, essential for addressing system-wide vulnerabilities, remains underdeveloped. Additionally, political and institutional pressures pose risks to maintaining robust regulatory frameworks, with ongoing debates over deregulation potentially undermining post-crisis gains.

The crisis exposed critical flaws in the global financial system, from unchecked lending practices and regulatory loopholes to over-reliance on opaque financial instruments and inadequate oversight. The crisis triggered unprecedented interventions and reforms, which introduced sweeping measures to enhance financial stability, address systemic risks, and protect consumers. While these reforms significantly strengthened the resilience of financial institutions, unresolved challenges such as shadow banking and political pressures for deregulation highlight the ongoing need for vigilance and adaptive policymaking to safeguard the stability of the financial system in the future.

Chapter 3 Research Philosophy and Methodological Foundation

Understanding the philosophical foundation of research is significant since they impact all phases of the process, from developing research questions to interpreting results. Research philosophy's fundamental concerns are the nature of reality, Ontology, the process of acquiring knowledge, Epistemology, and the role of values in shaping research, Axiology, in shaping the research process. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019)

The methodology, including research design, data collection techniques and methods of analysis, is directly influenced by these philosophical presumptions. Hence, the study uses the Research Onion Framework developed Saunders. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019)

(Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p.174)

Chapter 3.1: Pragmatism as the Research Philosophy

The core research philosophy of this study is pragmatism, that reflects the necessity for both depth and flexibility when addressing the complicated subject matter of financial regulatory failures and crisis management. By placing more emphasis on the research topic and real-world implications than effective effort to a single worldview, pragmatic philosophy provides a medium ground between positivism and interpretivism. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, pp.144–145) Through performing that, it allows researchers to use the best tools from various methodological traditions to comprehend both context-specific policy responses and quantitative financial data.

The dual nature of financial crises requires a pluralistic approach to methodology in the research. Economic models, risk measurements, and performance indicators can all be used to objectively evaluate financial systems. Moreover, institutional behaviors, environment, and interpretive policy narratives all have a significant influence on regulatory decisions, these factors call for a qualitative context-sensitive approaches. Nevertheless, this balance is supported by pragmatics which makes it possible to apply both inductive reasoning, from extracting insights from case studies of financial governance to deductive reasoning for testing established regulatory theories using actual evidence. (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004)

Other philosophical paradigms, such as positivism, interpretivism, and critical theory, where taken into consideration but eventually rejected because of their inability to meet the study's dual analytical requirements. Although positivism is strong in quantitative research, it ignores the interpretive and contextual subtleties of regulatory behavior and concentrates only on quantifiable events. (Lukenchuk, 2017; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). On the other hand, interpretivism performs excellently of comprehending, meanings that are socially created, but it is unable to manage the objective analysis of financial data that is required for this study. Although critical theory provides insightful viewpoints on emancipation and power, its ideological emphasis is incompatible with the pragmatic, goal-oriented goals of this study.

Pragmatism, on the other hand, accepts both empirical data and interpretive insights, enabling the researcher to move without contradiction between socially produced meanings, such as institutional narratives, and objective realities, such as regulatory measurements. It adopts a dual ontological position that values both built and quantifiable realities. It endorses a problem-centered, consequence-driven approach to knowledge development from an epistemological standpoint (Lukenchuk, 2017). From an axiological perspective, pragmatism maintains analytical integrity while acknowledging the existence of researcher values and encouraging reflexivity. (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, p.145)

Following that, pragmatism provides the best philosophical underpinning for this research because of its adaptability in terms of methodology, emphasis on real-world problem-solving, and capacity to integrate quantitative and qualitative approaches. The recognition of the importance of both empirical analysis and interpretive depth allows for a comprehensive investigation of financial regulatory failures, guaranteeing that the research is both rigorous and applicable to real-world situations.

Chapter 3.2: Research Design and Approach

By using both **Deductive** and **Inductive** reasoning, this study takes a hybrid research approach that is consistent with its pragmatic philosophical underpinnings. By examining quantitative financial indicators like ratios of debt to GDP, financial assets metrics, and mortgage default rates, deductive reasoning is used to examine established theories about financial crisis and regulatory deficiencies. On the other hand, using qualitative case studies of institutional behavior during financial crises, inductive reasoning is employed to investigate how regulatory actors defined and mishandled systemic risk. In addition to confirming theoretical presumptions, this dual-mode reasoning reveals emerging patterns rooted in complex real-world situations. (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004, p.17; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019, pp.152–155)

The research uses a merging parallel mixed-methods approach, which collects both quantitative and qualitative data at the same time, to apply the dual logic. After being individually examined, these data streams are combined to produce meta-inferences, which are findings that combine statistical trends with in-depth analysis. By combining contextual institutional narratives with actual financial patterns, this methodological decision enables an in-depth understanding of the research subject.

According to Venkatesh, Brown, and Bala (2013, pp.25–30), mixed methods are especially useful for examining intricate socio-technical systems, like financial markets, where reality is co-constructed by human interpretation and numerical data. They suggest that, particularly when addressing both confirmatory (deductive) and exploratory (inductive) aims, merging mixed-methods research makes it easier to create integrated, practical findings. The methodology makes sure that this study understands the socio-political narratives influencing institutional responses in addition to assessing the quantitative aspects of financial regulation failure.

In the end, this convergent mixed-methods approach and hybrid thinking ensure methodological coherence and enhance the study's ability to produce conclusions that are both theoretically sound and practically applicable.

Chapter 3.3: Research Strategy, Data collection, and Analysis

The research strategy for this study integrates empirical modeling with case-based analysis to fully capture the multi-dimensional nature of financial regulatory failures. On the quantitative side, using data from the Federal Reserve Economic Database (FRED), the Bank for International Settlements (BIS), and the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the study performs regression analysis and time-series modeling of important financial indicators, such as leverage ratios, mortgage default rates, and liquidity trends.

Python is the main computational tool used in the study to carry out the quantitative analysis. The data was cleaned, combined, shown, and statistically examined using Python's data science modules, including pandas, matplotlib, and stats models. This method guarantees that conclusions are supported by organized, traceable evidence and improves the results' analytical reliability, transparency, and reproducibility.

On the qualitative side, the study makes use of extensive institutional case studies that concentrate on significant organizations such as the Federal Reserve, AIG, Lehman Brothers, and Congressional oversight agencies. The Financial Crisis Inquiry Report (2010) and congressional legislation transcripts, such as the Dodd-Frank Act, serve as the foundation for these case studies. When combined, these approaches enable the study to evaluate the actual structure of systemic risk and to explain the shifts of regulatory narratives and decision-making processes over time. (Arner, 2009; Crotty, 2009b; Crotty, 2009a)

To support this multi-method approach, the study uses a longitudinal time horizon, tracking events over a broad historical period, often from the early 2000s to 2012, which represents the most active phase of the global financial crisis and its immediate regulatory aftermath. Pre-crisis accumulation, crisis impact, and post-crisis reform outcomes can all be observed thanks to this. Important regulatory changes like the Dodd-Frank Act and Basel III regulatory standards, which were designed to improve risk management practices and strengthen bank capital requirements globally, are examples of these changes.

According to Saunders et al.(2019, p.212), longitudinal studies offer a deeper comprehension of systemic changes over time and are especially well-suited for process-oriented and temporal assessments. This method provides a comprehensive picture of the development of financial governance by guaranteeing that both immediate reactions and long-term regulatory changes are recorded.

Additionally, this method approach is based on Mishkin's (2010) research, which emphasizes the necessity for more prepared risk-aware measures and the drawbacks of traditional monetary policy tools in times of crisis. His research backs the modeling framework's incorporation of credit tightening and monetary reactions. Tarullo (2019) offers a discussion of the post-crisis regulatory environment, highlighting the shortcomings of the existing legal frameworks, his research emphasizes the significance to evaluate both the formal reforms and the implication over time.

Thus, tactics, time-bound datasets, and rigorous analysis methods are all integrated in the research to create a strong methodological framework that can capture the institutional narratives and statistical regularities that underlie financial regulatory failures.

Chapter 3.4: Ethical Consideration and Research Limitations

The study uses only publicly available secondary data and complies with ethical guidelines both theoretically and practically. In every aspect of data selection, analysis, and reporting, it conforms the values of precision, openness, and institutional sensitivity. Legal and privacy issues are reduced when private or confidential information is absent.

Kjellström, Ross, and Fridlund (2010) provide guidance for reflexive practice, which forms the basis of ethical reasoning. It places a strong emphasis on responsibility in critique, fairness in interpretation, and awareness of researcher positionality. Marshall (1992) and Mauthner (2020) have contributed to the field of ethics by offering crucial guidance for conducting research in applied and institutionally sensitive contexts.

Limitations to the study, include limited access to private institutional data, which could limit understanding of the complex motivations behind policy decisions. Despite attempts to reduce bias through structured analysis using Python for data handling and content parsing, interpretive subjectivity is still considered when evaluating institutional texts thematically.

Although the study's U.S.-centric focus limits its universality, comparative references to frameworks like Basel III increase its contextual relevance. In accordance with ethical guidelines for studies involving public sector critique, institutional sensitivity has been preserved when analyzing errors and choices. These restrictions and moral considerations uphold openness in institutional and policy-related research and are consistent with the suggestions made by Mauthner (2020), Marshall (1992), and Kjellström et al. (2010).

Chapter 4: Findings, Analysis and Discussion.

The findings of the research are presented and interpreted in this chapter using both quantitative and qualitative methods. The chapter examines the systemic causes and regulatory ramifications of the 2008 global financial crisis by combining statistical analysis with thematic case interpretation, which is consistent with the pragmatist research philosophy. Examining how market instability was caused by insufficient financial oversight, institutional fragility, and a delayed policy response—as well as how post-crisis reforms have attempted to rectify these shortcomings.

Chapter 4.1: Quantitative Results

To find trends, test economic theories, and provide forecasts on the dynamics of financial crises, this study heavily relies on advanced quantitative analysis techniques. The study combines time-series models, regression analysis and correlation matrices to examine systemic vulnerabilities across pre- and post-crisis periods, in keeping with the guidelines of Shmueli and Koppius (2011), who emphasizes predictive analytics is essential for developing theories, testing theories, and determining the applicability of empirical phenomena, this study combines regression analysis, correlation matrices, and time-series models to examine systemic vulnerabilities in both pre- and post-crisis eras.

The analysis also integrates important macroeconomic (GDP, CPI, UNRATE) and institutional (Asset, Quality, Bankruptcy tendencies) variables to identify hidden warnings using Chen, Chiang, and Storey's (2012) Business Intelligence and Analytics framework. Early indicators of financial instability are revealed by this methodical, data-driven approach, which also aids in the development of more adaptable regulatory measures.

Figure 4.1: Correlation Matrix During the 2007–2008 Crisis

The matrix illustrates the positive association between bankruptcy cases and declining assets quality, as well as the significant inverse relationships between GDP growth and Unemployment (UNRATE). The reduction in asset quality is strongly correlated with both bankruptcy cases and unemployment (UNRATE), suggesting a feedback loop between institutional risk and deteriorating economic fundamentals. Price instability during systemic shocks is reflected in the CPI (inflation), which also seems to vary inversely with GDP. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Figure 4.2: Correlation Matrix Post-Crisis (2009–2012)

Post-crisis correlations weakened significantly. The strong alignments found during the crisis have collapsed, with most variables showing weak or near-zero correlations. For example, the Asset Quality Index correlates only slightly with CPI (Consumer price index) and unemployment, whereas Bankruptcy Cases have no substantial relationship with macroeconomic variables. This suggests a more fragmented, potentially policy-driven stabilization period in which market dynamics diverge

from traditional economic indicators. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Figure 4.3: Correlation Matrix Pre-Crisis (2000–2006)

Prior to the crisis, correlations between fundamental indicators were moderate. For example, unemployment and CPI are adversely connected, although GDP growth has minor positive links with CPI and small inverse trends with asset quality. Importantly, Bankruptcy Cases had a weak connection with fundamental macro trends, implying that systemic warning signs were not clear or linked, thus explaining regulatory laxity. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Figure 4.4: Bankruptcy Cases – Pre vs Post 2008

Graph shows a significant shift in bankruptcy case trends during the 2007-2008 crisis. Prior to the crisis, bankruptcy filings were reasonably constant, with swings in the 35,000-40,000 range. However, soon after 2008, registrations surpassed 60,000, signaling a wave of institutional and consumer financial turmoil. This post-crisis increases, followed by a slow drop, illustrates both the

delayed effects of economic shocks and the ultimate impact of fiscal and monetary policy initiatives. Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.

Figure 4.5: Fiscal EMV (Equity Market Volatility) Index – Pre vs Post 2008

This graph depicts a substantial increase in fiscal uncertainty that coincided with the 2007-2008 financial crisis. While fiscal EMV levels fluctuated but remained mild prior to the crisis, they increased dramatically in the post-crisis period, rising significantly beyond historical averages. This spike reflects the increased market fear and policy uncertainty that occurred throughout the bailout discussions and legislative negotiations. The steady decline after 2009 demonstrates temporary stabilization efforts, however levels remained elevated, indicating continuing fiscal and regulatory uncertainty. Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.

Figure 4.6: GDP Growth – Pre vs Post 2008

The graphic shows the stark contrast in GDP growth trends before and after the financial crisis. The pre-crisis period had relatively constant and positive GDP growth, with levels typically ranging between 2% and 5%, indicating a period of widespread economic prosperity. However, during the crisis, GDP growth became more variable, with a significant decline in 2009. Despite the eventual

recovery, the post-2008 era represents a sluggish and uneven economic trajectory. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Figure 4.7: Unemployment Rate (UNRATE) – Pre vs Post 2008

The statistic depicts a huge post-crisis increase in unemployment. Before the crisis, the unemployment rate ranged between 4% and 6%, with substantial cyclical volatility. However, in 2008, the percentage increased dramatically, peaking over 10% in 2009, reflecting extensive labor market disruptions and a delayed recovery in job circumstances. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Regression Outputs:

Figure 4.8: Scatter Plot – Bankruptcy Cases vs Unemployment Rate (UNRATE)

This scatter plot shows a significant positive linear link between bankruptcies and unemployment. The greater the number of bankruptcy filings, the higher the unemployment rate, implying that economic failure among institutions and people worsens labor market conditions. The linear fit line supports the predictive utility of bankruptcy cases in anticipating employment market stress. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Figure 4.9: Scatter Plot – CPI (Consumer Price Index) vs Unemployment Rate (UNRATE)

The following graph suggests an inverse association between inflation (CPI Total) and unemployment, which is consistent with the conventional Phillips Curve theory. Lower inflation tends to coincide with high unemployment, implying deflationary pressure during economic

downturns. However, the broad confidence range suggests that the model is rather uncertain. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Figure 4.10: Scatter Plot – GDP Growth vs Asset Quality Index

This scatter plot validates GDP as a strong macroeconomic indicator for institutional financial condition. A significant negative association exists between GDP growth and asset quality degradation. As GDP growth slows or reverses, asset quality deteriorates significantly—a predictable outcome during crisis periods when defaults rise. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Figure 4.11: Scatter Plot – GDP Growth vs CPI Total

Here, we see a moderately positive relationship between economic growth and inflation. As GDP rises, so does inflation, validating traditional economic concepts of demand-pull inflation. However, the dispersion of data points near the zero-growth threshold suggests more complicated processes during recessions. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Figure 4.12: Scatter Plot – GDP Growth vs Unemployment Rate (UNRATE)

As economic activity grows, unemployment tends to fall—another empirical reinforcement of Okun's Law. The constant falling trend highlights GDP's explanatory value in labor market analysis. This negative connection demonstrates the countercyclical nature of unemployment in respect to GDP growth. *Source: Author's analysis using data from FRED (Python). See Appendix A & A1.1 for full dataset list and code.*

Pre-/Post-Crisis Comparison:

The pre-crisis period (**2000-2006**) was characterized by more modest and less coordinated fluctuations in macroeconomic indices. Figure 4.3 shows that there is only a moderate relationship between asset quality, bankruptcy instances, and unemployment. Correlations are weak and not regularly aligned, which might explain why authorities failed to detect mounting hazards. GDP growth and CPI exhibited a small positive association, but asset quality looked to be constant.

In contrast, the crisis era (**2007-2008**) exhibits intense and clearly aligned ties. As seen in Figure 4.1, unemployment grows in unison with bankruptcy cases and deterioration in asset quality, while GDP growth and CPI fall dramatically. The level of correlation—such as UNRATE and Bankruptcy Cases (0.93) or UNRATE and Asset Quality (0.97)—indicates a feedback loop in which economic fragility worsens institutional breakdown and vice versa.

Systemic connections worsened following the crisis (**2009-2012**), as seen in Figure 4.2. Market indicators diverge, and most correlations fall dramatically, owing to governmental interventions,

stimulus programs, and regulatory change (e.g., the Dodd-Frank Act, Basel III) that disturbed previous patterns. For example, the formerly significant relationship between GDP growth and unemployment is essentially non-existent, implying that unemployment remained persistent even as GDP began to rise.

This comparison timeline confirms the crisis as an inflection moment. It shows a rapid transition from weakly connected indicators before 2008 to strongly related economic distress during the crisis, and eventually to decoupled, policy-buffered dynamics in the recovery phase.

The quantitative findings of this study give specific, data-driven insights that directly address the research topics and main areas of research. The increase in bankruptcy cases and asset quality degradation during the **2007-2008 crisis**, together with strong linkages between unemployment, GDP fall, and CPI declines, indicates the systemic impact of unregulated financial instruments and insufficient regulation.

Regression and scatter graphs demonstrate how regulatory gaps and market imbalances exacerbated systemic risk and institutional failures, such as the fall of Lehman Brothers. Post-crisis data shows significant structural adjustments followed policy reforms such as Dodd-Frank, though the effectiveness of these measures is still debated. This study adds to a larger understanding of how the crisis unfolded and what it suggests about the fragility of financial regulation by finding significant predictive indicators and inter-variable relationships. It statistically illustrates how shortcomings in supervision, risk management, and institutional resilience contributed to the development of vulnerabilities, providing vital insights for enhancing early warning systems and shaping future regulatory policy.

Chapter 4.2: Case Analysis

The section points at the qualitative evidence surrounding institutional failures and policy responses during the 2007-2008 financial crisis, with a particular emphasis on official secondary documentation such as the FCIC report, Lehman Brothers testimonies, regulatory responses through the Dodd-Frank Act, and the liquidity and systemic risk insights from BIS and World Bank Group reports. These qualitative reports shed light on regulatory fragmentation, the failure of major institutions, and the reactive character of financial regulation during time of crisis. Additionally demonstrate the way international organizations changed their methods in response to gaps discovered during the crisis. While a more in-depth cross-analysis of these results with the quantitative patterns identified in Chapter 4.1 will be established in Chapter 4.3, several repeating signals, such as institutional failure coinciding with asset quality decline and growing insolvency, provide early conceptual links.

Institutional Failures and Oversight Breakdown

The fall of Lehman Brothers in September 2008 is widely regarded as the most important institutional failure of the crisis. According to the FCIC (2010), Lehman's fall was caused by excessive leverage, exposure to deteriorating mortgage-backed securities, and on unsustainable reliance on short-term liquidity. The Lehman Examiner's Report and following Congressional testimony (Anon, 2010c) highlights numerous major lapses:

1. Excessive risk-taking in the subprime and commercial real estate sectors.
2. Using aggressive accounting techniques like Repo 105 to conceal leverage levels.
3. Insufficient control by the SEC's Consolidated Supervised Entities (CSE) program.

The actions sent shockwaves across financial markets and sparked widespread instability, exposing a significant supervision gap at the highest regulatory levels. These institutional difficulties correspond to the larger market signals seen in the quantitative data, including the reduction in asset quality and increase in bankruptcy filings.

Regulatory Gaps and Government Interventions

The Citigroup instance shows the financial system's vulnerability and reliance on government backing. Despite receiving 25 billion dollars from the Troubled Asset Relief Program (TARP), Citigroup's stock price dropped owing to rising losses. The US Treasury, Federal Reserve, and FDIC intervened with 20 billion dollar capital infusion and asset guarantees totaling 301 billion dollars (Hoffner and Arnold, 2024). This rescue package was remarkable in size and scope, highlighting regulators lack of preventative instruments.

Instead of implementing a comprehensive regulatory plan, authorities were compelled to take reactive actions. The difference in treatment of Lehman Brothers and Citigroup exemplifies how crisis management judgments were frequently improvised rather than driven by clear legal frameworks. These institutional reactions may be evaluated considering the volatility patterns mentioned in Chapter 4.1, both before and after the crisis.

Role and Limitations of Existing Frameworks (Pre-Dodd-Frank)

The FCIC (2010) and Schapiro (2010) both stated that previous to the crisis, US financial supervision was fragmented and ineffective. Coordination deficiencies among regulators produced vulnerabilities that allowed institutions to engage in risk financial activities unnoticed.

Even before the crisis broke out, the BIS (2006) warned of liquidity concerns and structural weaknesses in cross-border financial organizations. These problems were largely neglected by the Basel II framework, which prioritized capital adequacy above liquidity of systemic interconnection. This resulted in unregulated procyclical lending insufficient buffers, and ineffective macroprudential monitoring.

Post-Crisis Regulatory Reforms: Dodd-Frank and Basel III

In response to the financial crisis, two major regulatory frameworks emerged to address systemic failures: the Dodd-Frank Wall Street Reform and Consumer Protection Act in the United States and the global Basel III framework, led by the Bank for International Settlements (BIS).

The Dodd-Frank Act (2013a) was introduced as a sweeping overhaul of financial regulation, aimed at tackling the vulnerabilities exposed by the 2007–2008 collapse. As highlighted by Forbes Advisor (2023) and Sumsb (2021), its primary goals were to enhance consumer protection and reduce systemic risk. To achieve this, it established new watchdogs such as the Financial Stability Oversight Council (FSOC) and the Consumer Financial Protection Bureau (CFPB), while introducing rigorous standards for transparency in derivatives markets, capital buffers, and institutional risk governance.

The legislation also set out to dismantle the idea that some institutions were "too big to fail." It introduced stress testing requirements and expanded oversight to include nonbank financial entities. But as noted by the University of Chicago Law Review (2020), these changes weren't universally embraced. There was significant political friction, with critics arguing that the Act placed heavy compliance burdens on smaller banks and created uncertainty around how nonbanks should be regulated.

Meanwhile, on the global front, the BIS responded by rolling out the Basel III reforms—arguably the most substantial rethinking of global banking rules in decades. These reforms aimed to boost the resilience of financial systems worldwide. Some of the key changes included:

- **Raising capital requirements and establishing minimum liquidity** levels to shield banks from potential shocks. The minimum common equity tier 1 (CET1) capital requirement was increased to 7%, including the conservation buffer, but most Group 1 banks now maintain an average CET1 ratio of more than 12%, according to BIS. (2025)
- **Stress testing** for systemically important institutions and stricter supervision frameworks will ensure that globally important banks are more resilient to poor market circumstances and local vulnerabilities. (BIS, 2010a)
- **Introduction of the Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR)** to ensure banks hold enough high-quality liquid assets to withstand a 30-day liquidity crisis. While the global average LCR for Group 1 banks was 132.3%, three institutions still reported ratios below the 100% minimum (BIS 2025)
- **The Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR)**, which promotes stable, long-term funding strategies. The average NSFR among Group 1 banks was 123.6%, indicating overall progress toward meeting longer-term liquidity needs (BIS, 2025)

- **A stronger focus on macroprudential regulation**, including countercyclical capital buffers and jurisdictional discretion in mitigating systemic risks. These tools allow national authorities to address country-specific financial stress and excessive credit growth more effectively (BIS, 2010b; BIS, 2025)

Together, Dodd-Frank and Basel III signaled a move from narrow, institution-level oversight to a broader, macro-level approach that considers systemic risk across the entire financial landscape. Despite their ambition, however, implementation has not been without its challenges. BIS reports and congressional evaluations point to inconsistencies in how these reforms have been applied across countries, limitations in data availability, and the continued growth of shadow banking as key factors that hinder their full effectiveness.

Chapter 4.3: Integrated Discussion

This chapter explores and establishes the study's findings within the larger theoretical debate of financial crises and regulatory failure. Using both quantitative and qualitative case evidence, it critically examines how systemic flaws, regulatory failures, and delayed remedies contributed to the 2007-2008 financial crisis. It also evaluates the effectiveness of post-crisis reforms.

Systemic Risk and Institutional Fragility

The quantitative data, particularly Figures 4.1 and 4.8, show strong positive relationships between bankruptcy cases and unemployment, with asset quality deteriorating sharply during the crisis. This feedback loop supports Allen, Babus, and Carletti's (2009b) claim that institutional turmoil can severely reduce credit and economic growth. As unemployment surpassed 10% and GDP contracted (Figures 4.6 and 4.7), systemic vulnerabilities were exacerbated, underscoring the idea that banking crises are inextricably tied to economic cycles and can become self-reinforcing.

This aligns with **Mishkin (2010)** who emphasizes how poorly understood financial innovations and weak regulation of subprime lending exacerbated systemic risk. The evidence presented in this thesis supports Mishkin's claim that regulatory oversight failed to anticipate the interdependencies between consumer defaults and broader economic contraction.

Regulatory Failure and the Role of Oversight

The discussion further validates the findings from **Johnson and Kwak (2010)** and **Acharya and Richardson (2009)**, who critique the dismantling of protective measures like the Glass-Steagall Act and the unchecked expansion of subprime lending. As shown in the literature review, deregulation facilitated the rise of **Structured Investment Vehicles (SIVs)** and **private-label MBS**, which masked underlying risks. The significant spike in bankruptcy cases (Figure 4.4) and volatility (Figure 4.5) demonstrates the tangle of outcomes of these flawed instruments.

Furthermore, the pre-crisis correlation matrix (Figure 4.3) shows weak or inconsistent relationships between key macroeconomic indicators, implying that early warning signs were either invisible or ignored by regulators — a point echoed by Crotty (2009a), who criticized the "originate and distribute" model for embedding fragility deeply within the system.

Institutional Case Failures

Qualitative case analysis of **Lehman Brothers' collapses**, and **AIG's bailout** underscores the institutional unpreparedness highlighted in the **Financial Crisis Inquiry Report (United States, 2010)**. These cases embody the failure to enforce adequate capital reserves, stress testing, and risk transparency. The findings in Figure 4.1, where asset quality and unemployment are tightly linked, further validate the idea that **weak regulatory guardrails** allowed risk to accumulate unchecked.

The **Federal Reserve's response**, as discussed by **Khademian (2011)**, including quantitative easing and emergency lending facilities, came as a necessary but **reactive solution**. These measures, while stabilizing markets, did not address the root cause — a **systemically flawed oversight framework**.

Post-Crisis Stabilization and Reforms

The post-crisis period (2009–2012) revealed much weaker correlations across key variables (Figure 4.2), implying that reforms such as the Dodd-Frank Act and Basel III disrupted traditional market dynamics. While this may indicate stabilization, it also suggests policy-driven fragmentation, in which intervention, rather than market fundamentals, affected behavior.

According to Baily, Klein, and Schardin (2017), the Dodd-Frank Act aimed to reduce systemic risk by improving oversight and consumer protection. The findings here support the idea that key provisions, including as the Volcker Rule, FSOC, and Orderly Liquidation Authority, contributed to protect against a second wave of systemic failure.

Moreover, consistent with **Tarullo (2019)**, vulnerabilities in shadow banking, as well as continued political resistance to regulation, provide concerns. Unemployment remained high in the post-crisis period despite moderate GDP growth (Figures 4.6 & 4.7), demonstrating that structural harm to labor markets continued — a reality that reforms alone could not immediately alter.

The scatter plots (Figures 4.10-4.12) support traditional macroeconomic theories such as Okun's Law and the Phillips Curve by illustrating the predictive power of indicators such as unemployment and GDP growth in judging economic health. The high correlation between asset quality and GDP reduction (Figure 4.10) demonstrates that financial hardship has a direct and observable macroeconomic impact, supporting the adoption of predictive analytics frameworks such as those outlined by Chen, Chiang, and Storey (2012)

By identifying such leading indications, the study supports Shmueli and Koppius' (2011) demand for regulatory authorities to implement early warning systems based on quantitative modeling, particularly when dealing with complex, data-rich environments such as modern financial markets.

With all factors considered, the study's conclusions are in line with critical theories and empirical studies on the crisis, emphasizing how institutional opacity, unregulated financial innovation, and regulatory inertia set off a chain reaction of market failure. Even while financial resilience has increased because of post-crisis reforms, ongoing attention is crucial, especially considering institutional and political demands for deregulation. The integrated discussion supports the thesis aim, which holds that the lessons learned from the 2007–2008 crisis are still very applicable today and that it was not only a market failure but also a governance failure.

Chapter 5: Conclusion

With an emphasis on regulatory shortcomings in the supervision of subprime loans and mortgage-backed securities, the interdependence of banking and financial crises, and the efficacy of post-crisis reforms, this study aimed to explore the systemic causes of the financial crisis of 2007–2008. The research has offered a thorough understanding of how faulty regulation, institutional vulnerabilities, and postponed policy responses contributed to one of the worst economic downturns in modern history through a convergent mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative financial modeling with qualitative institutional analysis.

During the crisis, quantitative analysis showed distinct patterns of systemic suffering. Strong relationships between deteriorating asset quality, increasing bankruptcy rates, GDP contraction, and rising unemployment were shown using correlation matrices and regression results. These results support the idea that regulators either ignored or undervalued early warning indicators of market imbalances. The absence of reliable early warning systems was highlighted by pre-crisis data showing weak and erratic relationships between important economic indices. These indicators, on the other hand, showed a strong alignment throughout the crisis, indicating that systemic risk had permeated financial institutions and markets.

These observations were corroborated by qualitative research using case studies of Citigroup, AIG, and Lehman Brothers. These instances demonstrated how high-risk financial activities were able to thrive unchecked due to enormous leverage, a lack of transparency, and inadequate regulation, especially by the Federal Reserve and the SEC. The current regulatory environment's vulnerability was made clear by the collapse of centralized supervisory structures and the need for discretionary emergency interventions like the Troubled Asset Relief Program (TARP).

The Dodd-Frank Act and the Basel III framework, which brought about post-crisis reforms, were also evaluated in the study. Through increased liquidity buffers, capital requirements, macroprudential supervision, and consumer protection, these policies sought to increase systemic resilience. Even though these efforts have improved the regulatory environment, the results show that problems still exist, particularly in areas like shadow banking and political pressure for deregulation. Additionally, the post-crisis period's continued high unemployment rates and modest economic growth underscore the long-lasting effects of structural flaws that regulation by itself was unable to effectively address.

Overall, this study concludes that the financial crisis of 2007–2008 was caused by both a major governance failure and market failures. The absence of prompt policy response, institutional fragility, and regulatory deficiencies all contributed to the self-reinforcing cycle of financial instability. Even if many risks have been addressed by post-crisis reforms, constant attention to detail and adaptability are necessary to guarantee the global financial system's resilience. These observations are still applicable if the world's financial systems are confronted with fresh and changing problems.

Chapter 5.1: Recommendation

The study's conclusions suggest that to spot early indicators of systemic instability, regulatory agencies should combine data-driven monitoring systems with predictive analytics. Shadow banking and nonbank financial organizations that presently function in regulatory gray areas, should be subject to broader oversight. Global financial risk management requires better coordination between national and international regulatory bodies. To assess institutional resilience under various economic scenarios, macroprudential stress testing should also be established as a standard preventive tool. To restore public confidence and uphold market discipline, transparency in risk assessments and regulatory choices needs to be improved. Lastly, to learn from cross-border crises and get a deeper understanding of the efficacy of regulations in various financial systems, future study should take a comparative international approach.

The financial crisis of 2007–2008 was an important phase in the history of the world economy. It made clear the complex and frequently fragile relationships that exist between institutional behavior, regulation design, and market dynamics. The structures and regulations that oversee financial systems must change along with them. The necessity of flexible, data-driven, and morally sound regulation is reaffirmed by this study. With more foresight and readiness, future crises can be predicted, if not completely avoided, by adopting forward-looking tactics and learning from errors that have occurred previously.

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Appendixes: A Datasets:

A1	Asset Quality Measures 2007 – 2010	FRED
A2	Consumer price indices US 2000 – 2010	FRED
A3	CPI total US 2000 – 2010	FRED
A4	EMV Tracker - Fiscal policy 2000 – 2007	FRED
A5	EMV Macroeconomic News and Outlook - Inflation 2000 – 2010	FRED
A6	EMV Tracker Financial Crisis 2000 – 2010	FRED
A7	EMV Tracker Interest Rates 2000 – 2010	FRED
A8	EMV Tracker Monetary Policy 2000 – 2010	FRED
A9	EMV Tracker Real Estate Markets 2000 – 2010	FRED
A10	Equity Market Volatility Tracker Overall 2000 – 2010	FRED
A11	Expenditure Distribution US on TARP	FRED
A12	Federal Funds Effective Rate 2000 – 2010	FRED
A13	GDP US 1990 – 2023	FRED
A14	Inflation CP for US 2000 – 2010	FRED
A15	Interest rates - Discount rates US 2000 – 2010	FRED
A16	Interest rates and Price Indexes - Commercial Real Estate price index 2000 – 2010	FRED
A17	Interest Rates and Price Indexes 2000 – 2010	FRED
A18	Largest Bankruptcies US	FRED
A19	Lehman Brothers Stock prices 1995 – 2008	FRED
A20	MMF – Total financial assets and levels 2000 – 2010	FRED
A21	Net % of Domestic Banks Reporting Stronger Demand for Subprime Mortgage Loans 2007 – 2012	FRED
A22	Net % of Domestic Banks Tightening Standards for Subprime Mortgage Loans 2007 – 2012	FRED
A23	Net % of Large Domestic Banks Tightening Standards for Subprime Mortgage Loans 2007 – 2012	FRED
A24	Number of Bankruptcy cases 2000 – 2023	FRED
A25	Poverty rate US 1990 – 2023	FRED
A26	Reserve Bank Credit - Central Bank Liquidity Swaps 2002 – 2012	FRED
A27	Stock Market Turnover Ratio Value Traded – Capitalization 2000 – 2011	FRED
A28	UNRATE for US 2000 – 2010	FRED

Appendix A1.1 – Python Code for Quantitative Analysis

The annotated Python script used to clean, process, and analyze the 28 financial datasets listed in Appendix A is accessible in this appendix. Every step involved in time-series modeling, regression, correlation analysis, and figure plotting used in Chapter 4.1 is covered in the script.

Primary Analysis, Script 1: [Analysis](#)

Quantitative Analysis, Script 2: [quant_analysis.py](#)

Core Activities done using the script:

- Data loading from all 28 **.xlsx** files
- Cleaning and transforming second sheet (**Sheet2**) for consistency
- Generating Figures 4.1 to 4.12 using: **pandas, matplotlib, seaborn, statsmodels**
- Pre- vs post-crisis comparative plotting
- Regression and correlation matrix visualizations

Appendix B: Preliminary Plots from Raw Dataset Analysis

B 1. Plot -

B 2. Plot -

B 3. Plot -

B 4. Plot -

B 5. Plot -

B 6. Plot -

B 7. Plot -

B 8. Plot -

B 9. Plot -

B 10. Plot -

B 11. Plot -

B 12. Plot -

B 13. Plot -

B 14. Plot -

B 15. Plot -

B 16. Plot -

B 17. Plot -

B 18. Plot -

B 19. Plot -

B 20. Plot -

B 21. Plot -

B 22. Plot -

B 23. Plot -

B 24. Plot -

B 25. Plot -

B 26. Plot -

B 27. Plot -

B 28 Plot –

